

European Human Exposome **NETWORK**

Translating Evidence into Policy

EHEEN

Report 9: Update to Policy Strategy

Period: M55-M60

Update to Joint strategy for science to policy translation of the scientific evidence generated by the network.

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Summary

This document provides an update to the previously outlined strategy for the European Human Exposome Network (submitted as Report 8), to collect and translate scientific evidence generated within its nine individual projects into formats that can be used in the policy-making process. Together, the projects not only cover a wide range of topics and different aspects of the exposome but also their results might influence various stakeholders across a variety of policy issues.

This document lays out a methodological approach for EHEN and the nine projects to work together to identify the areas where their scientific evidence can contribute; how to identify relevant stakeholders; analyse and comprise evidence, disseminate findings in various formats, and engage with stakeholders through events to support the policy-making process.

Introduction

The European Human Exposome Network¹ (EHEN) is the world's largest network of projects studying the impact of environmental exposure on human health.

It brings together nine research and innovation projects, receiving over €100 million from Horizon 2020, the EU's framework programme for research and innovation. Using exposome research approaches, these projects address the impact on health resulting from various combined exposures such as air pollution, noise, chemicals, microbes, and exposure related to urbanisation (including social factors). The projects' results will contribute to advancing the European Green Deal's² ambition and related policies (chemical strategy for sustainability; zero pollution action plan; 8th environment action plan; strategic Framework for Health and safety at work; EU's biodiversity strategy for 2030, urban health and noise), to protect citizens from pollution and environmental deterioration by providing new evidence for better preventive policies toward improving citizens' health and well-being, while reducing inequalities. In Table 1 an overview is given of which project could contribute to the various policies.

The exposome describes all external and internal factors that can influence our health, from (before) birth until death. External factors include, for example, the environment, nutrition and diet, lifestyle, workplace, infections, etc. The nine EHEN projects study different aspects of the exposome and the impact it has on various areas of health and society.

The EHEN projects

ATHLETE measures many environmental exposures (urban, chemical, lifestyle, and social risk factors) during pregnancy, childhood, and adolescence and links them to children's biological responses and cardiometabolic, respiratory, and mental health.

athleteproject.eu

EPHOR studies the exposomic factors during the working-life. Their research will contribute to reducing the burden of Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) on EU healthcare systems, improving the health and wellbeing of EU citizens, improving the productivity of the EU workforce, and increasing the competitiveness of EU industry.

ephor-project.eu

Equal-Life develops and tests combined exposure data using a novel approach to multi-modal exposures and their impact on children's mental health and development.

¹ <https://www.humanexposome.eu/>

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/communication-european-green-deal_en

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	<p>equal-life.eu</p> <p>EXIMIOUS maps exposome, immune system (immunome), other omics, and clinical and socio-economic data to identify ‘immune fingerprints’ that are early signs of poor health and predictors of disease at the individual level.</p> <p>eximious-h2020.eu</p>
	<p>EXPANSE aims to decrease the proportion of unexplained Cardio-Metabolic and Pulmonary Disease (CMPD) risk in urban populations and to gain insights into mediating biological mechanisms and causality.</p> <p>expanseproject.eu</p>
	<p>HEDIMED identifies exposomic determinants, which are driving the rapid increase of immune-mediated diseases (IMDs) such as type 1 diabetes, celiac disease, allergies and asthma.</p> <p>hedimed.eu</p>
	<p>HEAP provides an efficient platform (including informatics infrastructure and software platform) for handling and analysing large amounts of data on environmental exposures and their health effects.</p> <p>heap-exposome.eu</p>
	<p>LongITools is studying the interactions between the environment, lifestyle and health throughout the life-course in determining people’s risks of developing chronic cardiovascular and metabolic diseases</p> <p>longitools.org</p>
	<p>REMEDIA studies the contribution of the exposome on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and cystic fibrosis (CF).</p> <p>h2020-remedia.eu</p>

This document outlines the policy areas where at least two EHEN projects may contribute and that a coordinated approach in the context of the EHEN is then relevant. As Table 1 below indicates, the outcome of the individual EHEN projects might have an impact on specific groups or topics, they may affect certain policy areas and contribute to the advancement of existing policies. These include, but are not limited to air, environment, nature and biodiversity, noise, health, urban environment and social environment.

Policy areas and strategies

The *EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability towards a toxic-free environment* aims to better protect citizens and the environment boost innovation for safe and sustainable chemicals³

The aim of the *Zero pollution action plan - Towards zero pollution for air, water and soil* is for air, water and soil pollution to be reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems, that respect the boundaries with which our planet can cope, thereby creating a toxic-free environment.⁴

The long-term aim of the *Environment action programme to 2030 - The 8th Environment Action Programme* will guide European environmental policy until 2030 is that, by 2050 at the latest, Europeans live well, within planetary boundaries, in a well-being economy where nothing is wasted. Growth will be regenerative, climate neutrality will be a reality, and inequalities will have been significantly reduced.⁵

The *EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at Work 2021-2027* defines the key priorities and actions for improving workers' health and safety, addressing rapid changes in the economy, demography and work patterns.⁶

The *Biodiversity strategy for 2030* is a plan to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems. The strategy aims to build our societies' resilience to future threats such as the impacts of climate change, forest fires, food insecurity, disease outbreaks - including by protecting wildlife and fighting illegal wildlife trade.⁷

Urban health aims at ensuring general well-being in cities by understanding how the urban environment affects health outcomes at both collective and individual level.⁸ The *WHO Urban Health Initiative* mobilises and empowers the health sector to promote the implementation of air and climate pollutant reduction strategies, provides tools and guidance for decision-makers to assess potential health benefits and health risks, and demonstrate to the public the full range of health, economic and climate benefits that can be achieved from implementing local emission reduction policies and strategies.⁹

EU noise policy aims to monitor and tackle environmental noise in Europe to help achieve the zero pollution vision for 2050. EU rules address noise pollution from the main sources, outdoor noise sources, as well as underwater noise affecting sea animals.¹⁰

³ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en

⁴ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/zero-pollution-action-plan_en

⁵ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/environment-action-programme-2030_en

⁶ <https://osha.europa.eu/en/safety-and-health-legislation/eu-strategic-framework-health-and-safety-work-2021-2027>

⁷ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

⁸ <https://urban.jrc.ec.europa.eu/thefutureofcities/urban-health#the-chapter>

⁹ <https://www.who.int/initiatives/urban-health-initiative>

¹⁰ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/noise_en

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Table 1. Overview of foreseen policy contributions of the different EHEN projects.

Relevant to	Policy/Policy area								
Topic	Chemicals	Environmental Pollution		H&S at work	Obesity	Biodiversity	Urban health	Cosmetics	Noise
Directives/Legislation	Chemicals strategy	EC Zero pollution action plan Ambient Air Quality Directives	8th Environment Action Programme	EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at Work 2021-2027	Childhood Obesity Action	EU's biodiversity strategy for 2030	Urban Health	EU Cosmetics Directive/Regulation (revised in 2022)	Noise
Health of children	HEDIMED ATHLETE EXPANSE	HEDIMED ATHLETE EQUAL-LIFE EXIMIOUS REMEDIA LONGITOOLS	HEDIMED ATHLETE EQUAL-LIFE EXIMIOUS EXPANSE REMEDIA LONGITOOLS		ATHLETE EXPANSE LONGITOOLS	HEDIMED	ATHLETE HEAP EQUAL-LIFE EXPANSE HEDIMED REMEDIA LONGITOOLS	ATHLETE	EQUAL-LIFE REMEDIA LONGITOOLS
Health of workers	EPHOR			EPHOR EXIMIOUS	LONGITOOLS		LONGITOOLS		LONGITOOLS EPHOR
Health of individual suffering from immune mediated disease	HEDIMED	HEDIMED EXIMIOUS	HEDIMED EXIMIOUS LONGITOOLS	EPHOR		HEDIMED	HEDIMED		
Non communicable diseases	EXPANSE HEDIMED EPHOR	HEDIMED REMEDIA	EXPANSE HEDIMED REMEDIA LONGITOOLS	EPHOR	LONGITOOLS	HEDIMED	EXPANSE HEAP HEDIMED LONGITOOLS		REMEDIA LONGITOOLS
Respiratory Disease	EXPANSE HEDIMED	REMEDIA HEDIMED	EXPANSE HEDIMED REMEDIA	EPHOR	LONGITOOLS	HEDIMED	EXPANSE HEDIMED REMEDIA LONGITOOLS		REMEDIA LONGITOOLS
Mental Health issues				EPHOR	LONGITOOLS		EQUAL-LIFE LONGITOOLS		LONGITOOLS

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Priorities of the next EU Commission and next EU policy cycle: 2024-2029

In early June 2024, the European Parliament elections took place, and a new EU Commission President and Commissioners will be nominated in the coming months. New EU policy priorities for the mandate 2024-2029 will also be set. These will be based on the EU's [Strategic Agenda](#) which outlines the EU political priorities for the future and is set to be adopted in June 2024.

The following policy milestones could be used as opportunities to provide EHEN evidence and results. These potential actions are to be discussed in the EHEN working groups before proceeding.

1. The new EU policy priorities by the new EU Commission President (July-Sept 2024). EHEN could consider providing the new EU Parliament and Commission Presidents with a letter outlining any EHEN evidence and briefing(s). The information provided could also be shared through EHEN and project partners' social media channels.
2. European Parliament hearings of the Commissioners-designate for Environment, Climate, Health (Oct-Nov 2024). A possible EHEN activity could be sharing data/statistics, evidence on how environmental exposures impact health, or information on the use of health impact assessment in spatial planning to identify health and wellbeing impacts, with political chairs who could use it to inform their members of the European Parliament when drafting questions to potential Commissioner nominees on implementing the Zero-Pollution, Chemicals Strategy or 8th EAP for the hearings for the new relevant Commissioners.

Due to the importance of the aforementioned policies and the impact these research projects can achieve, it is important to put a strategy in place to translate the scientific evidence into tangible and meaningful policy recommendations and to involve the relevant stakeholders. We will interact with the relevant EC Knowledge Centres (for example centre of cancer, centre of biodiversity etc) when appropriate. Also, if relevant, policies like the Healthier together initiative¹¹, Urban Agenda¹², and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), WHO Healthy Cities¹³, and national and local action plans will be considered.

This document lays out the EHEN strategy with updates for translating evidence into policy. We presented this joint strategy for transferring and translating the evidence generated by the nine exposome projects under the EHEN umbrella into

¹¹ https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d843d53e-c1c1-4664-b31e-febf618d011a_en?filename=eu-ncd-initiative_publication_en_0.pdf

¹²

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/brochure/urban_agenda_eu_2021update_en.pdf

¹³ <https://www.who.int/europe/groups/who-european-healthy-cities-network#:~:text=Healthy%20Cities%20approach,health%20at%20the%20local%20level.>

the policymaking process, thereby addressing current issues and providing recommendations for policy.

In addition, the EHEN network will exemplify and encourage the implementation of the exposome concept into health policies of which concrete examples could be:

- moving away from an approach that is based upon 'one chemical/stressor ...at one moment in time... causing one disease... as inferred by one analyte, one static sensor/single biomolecule assay',
- incorporating multiple and life-course exposures in prediction models
- recognizing the one-health concept as a way to improve human health and environmental health
- building diagnostics based on very detailed and precise biomolecules (omics)
- integrating personal sensor

In line with the EHEN projects, the focus of this strategy is on addressing policy for life-time exposures in relation to early life and child development, immune health, mental health, occupational health, urban health, cardiovascular and metabolic disease, and lung disease.

This document aims to propose a roadmap for an **updated common strategy** across the nine projects towards collectively informing and co-designing with stakeholders the policymaking process.

Background

The policymaking process is highly complex and consists of several stages ¹⁴. The stages encompass:

- Agenda setting
 - In this stage, policymakers identify and recognise problems.
- Policy formulation
 - Policymakers, together with the input of relevant stakeholders and other decision-makers, formulate policy options to tackle the identified problem. This stage describes how policies are agreed upon and formulated.
- Decision-making
 - A policy is enacted.
- Policy implementation
 - A policy is implemented/carried out.
- Monitoring and evaluation

¹⁴ See Buse, K. Mays, N. B. & Walt, G. (2012). Making Health Policy. Chapter 1: The health policy framework. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277890928_Making_Health_Policy

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- The impact of the policy is evaluated with respect to whether it achieves its objectives. Unintended effects of the policy can be uncovered at this stage. Policy change is initiated if necessary.¹⁵

This process is often presented as an iterative cycle (*Figure 1*).

*Figure 1: Policy Cycle*¹⁶

Evidence-informed policymaking puts forward the idea of informing this process by appraising the available (scientific) evidence allowing to ensure positive outcomes. This practice is “characterised by the fact that the access and appraisal of evidence as an input into the policymaking process is both systematic and transparent.”¹⁷ This means that systematic processes are utilised to “ensure that

¹⁵ See Buse, K. Mays, N. B. & Walt, G. (2012). Making Health Policy. Chapter 1: The health policy framework. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277890928_Making_Health_Policy

¹⁶ See for example Wellstead, A. & Stedman, R. (2015). Mainstreaming and Beyond: Policy Capacity and Climate Change Decision-Making. Available from:

<https://quod.lib.umich.edu/m/mjs/12333712.0003.003?view=text;rgn=main>

¹⁷ See Oxman, A. D., Levis, J. N., Lewin, S. & Fretheim, A. (2009). SUPPORT Tools for evidence-informed health Policymaking (STP) 1: What is evidence-informed policymaking? Available from: <https://health-policy-systems.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1478-4505-7-S1-S1>

research is identified, appraised and used appropriately” and that they are transparent “so that others can examine what research evidence has been used to inform policy decisions as well as the judgements made regarding the evidence and its implications”.¹⁸

Evidence-informed policymaking can encompass more than scientific studies and includes other sources of information apart from work developed under research projects. In a European context, the European Union (EU) aims to foster more evidence-informed policymaking through tools such as the Better Regulation guidelines and toolboxes.¹⁹ Evidence can inform all the stages of the policymaking cycle presented above.²⁰

It is important to note that the relationship between evidence and policy is not linear.²¹ This implies that policy decisions are not merely based on scientific evidence only, but that other factors also influence a policy’s ultimate **content**. Such factors include:

- Context
 - Situational factors, e.g., COVID-19
 - Structural factors, e.g., political system
 - Cultural factors, e.g., public perception and acceptance
 - International factors and context
 - Financial factors, e.g., availability of funding, sufficient cost-benefit analysis
 - Ethical and legal factors
 - (Scientific) frameworks for the collection of information
 - Socio-economic factors
- Process
 - E.g. policy cycle presented in Fig. 1
- Actors
 - E.g. Their personal agenda, interests, power and values

Thus, to promote an evidence-informed policymaking approach and to place research within the policy-making process, EHEN aimed to build a strategy for an

¹⁸ See Oxman, A. D., Levis, J. N., Lewin, S. & Fretheim, A. (2009). SUPPORT Tools for evidence-informed health Policymaking (STP) 1: What is evidence-informed policymaking? Available from: <https://health-policy-systems.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1478-4505-7-S1-S1>

¹⁹ See the European Commission website for more information on the Better Regulation Toolbox): https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation-why-and-how/better-regulation-guidelines-and-toolbox_en

²⁰ See Buse, K. Mays, N. B. & Walt, G. (2012). Making Health Policy. Chapter 9: Research, Evaluation and Policy. Available here:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277890928_Making_Health_Policy

²¹ See Buse, K. Mays, N. B. & Walt, G. (2012). Making Health Policy. Chapter 9: Research, Evaluation and Policy. Available here:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277890928_Making_Health_Policy

active network between researchers and policy makers so that relevant EHEN findings can be translated toward policy.

Figure 2: Policy Triangle²²

Several actionable steps were identified that EHEN researchers can take to foster the uptake of scientific and other evidence throughout the policymaking process.²³ Some of these steps are presented below:

- Identify relevant stakeholders
- Choose **research topics** important for future policy and address a need/opportunity.
- Undertake **systematic reviews** of research findings on policy-relevant questions to enable policymakers to access information more easily.
- Provide policy briefs
- Organise events such as **conferences, seminars, briefings and practical workshops** to disseminate research findings and inform policymakers about research.
- Identify **opinion leaders and innovators** and ensure they understand the research findings' implications.
- Keep in **close contact** with potential policy-makers throughout the research process.
- Create mechanisms to ensure the sustainability of established stakeholder interaction channels

²² See Walt, G. & Gilson, L. (1994). Reforming the health sector in developing countries: the central role of policy analysis. Available from:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10139469/>

²³ See Buse, K. Mays, N. B. & Walt, G. (2012). Making Health Policy. Chapter 9: Research, Evaluation and Policy. Available here:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277890928_Making_Health_Policy

Based on this background of the policy-making process, the nine EHEN projects jointly formulated a series of steps to be performed, and updates are provided on actions taken.

Steps taken by EHEN

Operational process

The Communication and Dissemination working group evolved at the start of 2023 to become the Communication, Dissemination and Policy working group (CDP WG). Each project of EHEN agreed to appoint a minimum of one policy representative by the first three months of 2023. The first meeting including the policy representatives was held in January 2023, and the CDP WG terms of reference were updated in May-23. Since the group’s set-up, 10 meetings were held.

The CDP WG will continue to have regular meetings to discuss the below identified steps and how to divide up work. The EHEN coordinating team is responsible for the organization of the meetings and will continue to chair them as per the agreed rotating leadership.

Months	Network coordinating team
M1 – M15	EXPANSE and HEAP
M16 – M30	ATHLETE and EQUAL-LIFE
M31 – M45	LONGITOOOLS and EXIMIOUS
M45 – M60	EPHOR, REMEDIA and HEDIMED

Table 2: schedule for rotating leadership of EHEN

Identification of Need/Opportunity

EHEN set out to periodically conduct a **mapping of the current relevant policy landscape** at the EU level. The subgroup is responsible for this, and this topic was discussed at different meetings.

Table 1 in this document was developed as part of the work carried out throughout 2023 of mapping current EU policies, and priorities where the evidence arising from EHEN might be relevant. This summary can also support discussions to identify windows of opportunity to share EHEN results with policymakers and place EHEN topics on the policymaking agenda.

Consequently, EHEN can **identify findings which are relevant to the policy discourse** across their projects and know which policy stakeholders to target with their dissemination efforts. To identify topics that could be presented to policymakers, the expected and obtained results of the projects should be analysed. This will also allow for the identification of potential gaps in the current research fields.

Altogether, EHEN covers a wide range of various exposome fields and health outcomes that fall into these high-level categories. EHEN reviews these opportunities based on the research outcomes and the following impact criteria:

- WHY are the research findings relevant for a specific topic?

- WHAT are the consequences of this research?
- HOW can policymaking take up this research?

Synthesis of Information

EHEN initially suggested to deliver 2-3 policy or information briefs, focussing on the suggested subjects below. Based on progress, the final number of briefs may need to be adjusted.

1. the potential contribution of EHEN to different policies,
2. specific areas that are developed by EHEN,
3. the future of exposome research.

The first brief was developed in 2023 and it is expected to be finalised at the end of 2024.

EHEN will discuss how to provide input on future plans for exposome research as work in this area will continue in the scope of the new International Human Exposome Network (IHEN) project. One of IHEN project's objectives is to develop a roadmap for future exposome research and innovation, based on interactions with European and global stakeholders.

Throughout 2023, the working group met several times to discuss possible outlines and the structure for the first brief and how to best reflect the potential contribution of EHEN to different policies, such as the Zero Pollution Action Plan of the European Commission (ZPAP) (see also Table 1). After discussions in the network and with the EC, it was decided to focus on demonstrating the potential outcomes and impacts of EHEN, through an overview of what the different EHEN projects have done across several areas of exposome research. The group asked all partner projects to complete a table to gather input on the different aspects of the exposome that the projects' research focuses on, and to share findings and existing knowledge that have been generated (such as publications, tools). Using this information, a set of common topics were identified to summarize the current state of research and what EHEN has achieved. These topics include the following:

Environment and Health:

- Rural and urban environment, built environment, environmental noise, natural environment - land cover, green and blue spaces.
- Indoor environment
- Chemical exposures, toxicants
- Air quality / pollution
- Water quality / pollution

Social, work, personal exposome and Health:

- Personal exposome, lifestyle and behaviour
- Food and nutrition
- Occupational exposome
- Socioeconomic, sociodemographic

Internal Exposome and Health:

- Biomarkers
- Epigenetics

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- Metabolome
- Microbiome
- Ageing and stress

In late May 2024, the project papers submitted were summarized in relation to the above topics and a draft text was circulated. The EHEN projects are in the process of providing input to the different sections of the draft. These will then be unified to come up with key messages around reducing exposures and health impacts.

In general, the approach applied has been to highlight similarities and differences between the projects to ensure an encompassing view of the findings. Concrete implications of the findings for policy will be presented whenever possible. This approach to information synthesis will ensure accessibility of information to policymakers as well as other parties influencing the policymaking process, such as interest groups.

Stakeholder Engagement

Both, EHEN internal and external stakeholders need to be engaged throughout the policymaking process to ensure that evidence can inform policy.

EHEN Internal Stakeholders

Within EHEN, the following stakeholders will be engaged:

- EHEN Network Advisory Board
- Policy experts from different EHEN projects/institutes
- Project researchers within the 9 projects

This will allow the network to **harness expertise and build a sound knowledge base** when engaging in policy-informing activities.

External Stakeholders

The main target group for this strategy of translating scientific evidence are **policymakers**.

Nevertheless, **third parties** can also influence the policymaking process. These include:

- Regulatory authorities and guidelines committees
- Governmental actors
- Other scientists and researchers
- Private sector/industry
- Social and environmental groups
- General public
- Patients and risk groups
- Consumer associations
- Health care sector
- Media

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The establishment of **formal and informal channels of communication** between EHEN, policymakers and policy influencers will allow for the identifying policy needs and **exchanging of knowledge and findings**. It will enable **solid relationships** between the parties.

One example of engagement across different levels and stakeholder groups has been through the use of periodic **campaigns**. In spring of 2023, a short focused social media campaign was run on the exposome during the lead up to the EHEN external stakeholder event in June 2023. This involved all EHEN projects sharing the same/similar weekly tweets for the five weeks prior to the event, to share key messages and encourage attendance. To promote public engagement, in December 2023, the HEAP communications team launched a short online [citizen quiz "Your exposome"](#), to find out the most pressing public concerns about the effect of the environment on health, and to gather feedback on exposome research topics. The quiz was shared through the network and replies indicated that air pollution and diet were the top concerns – with 80% of respondents worried about these exposures. Also high on the list were viruses, household chemicals and water quality.

Presentation and Dissemination of Results

Scientific evidence and lessons learnt from the projects have been presented in a **non-technical** manner in **different accessible formats**, such as newsletters, websites, social media posts, executive summaries, interim reports, including dissemination at the EHEN level via the EHEN website. Moreover, they will be adapted for **different policy maker categories** if possible. Documents will then be distributed in a timely manner to ensure the **currency of the information** with respect to the policymaking processes.

Besides policymakers, findings will also be distributed to influential stakeholders, such as interest groups, as they can also influence the policymaking process. The material to be shared will also include relevant infographics and research briefs.

Arrangements will be made with EHEN's communication and dissemination working group (C&D WG) to distribute evidence to **ensure streamlined efforts** and harness their expertise. Specifically, the policy subgroup within the C&D WG will be responsible for this process.

The [EHEN newsletters](#) remain an effective tool to provide summaries and updates on exposome research and projects' results which are shared widely at network level and across project channels.

Specific content on EHEN themes/topics has been developed and featured as part of the [EHEN blog series](#), that explains challenges and opportunities in the field of exposome research. Each project is responsible for one blog piece which is meant to target one of the key EHEN stakeholder groups.

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Events

In addition to one-way communication channels such as websites and publications, EHEN will plan **workshops and science policy meetings, webinars** with different audiences, if relevant, such as

1. High-level audiences: e.g., directors of regulatory/governmental health research institutes, EU, WHO, ECHA, EEA, (National) Ministries of Health, Directorates, and Members of the European Parliament.
2. Targeted audiences (together with project-specific satellites): e.g., Heads of branch organisations, patient groups, etc.

The policy subgroup of the C&D WG will be responsible for organising this further and when possible the European Commission will facilitate this process (e.g. by helping to organise a forum about policy making in relation to EHEN meetings or other high-level meetings).

One key EHEN event took place and another one is being planned so that projects can share scientific updates and results, and to have targeted discussions about exposome topics and links to policy action:

- [EHEN Scientific and external Stakeholder meeting](#) in Leuven, 30 May-1 June 2023 to discuss key aspects of relevant policies with representatives from EC, DG-RTD, DG EVN, and WHO, as well challenges of translating scientific findings into insights that could be used for policy development.
- EHEN Scientific and Stakeholder meeting in Brussels, 26-28 November 2024 – preparations for the event have started and the scientific and organizing committees have been established.

Toolbox

The Projects that make up the European Human Exposome Network each include the development of a toolbox both for **assessing and addressing the impact of environment on health** and **enabling researchers and policymakers to continuously include new knowledge in the policy-making processes** by using the toolbox to generate data and information.

Toolbox contents are specific to each project, and may include, for example, database and results catalogues, data collection protocols, analysis pipelines and protocols, health impact assessment and intervention toolkits, e-learning tutorials, and policy recommendations. Policymakers can use the toolbox for the development of evidence-based and cost-effective preventive policies and actions.

EHEN acknowledge that it is important to build an **inventory of tools** developed in all Projects, to avoid stakeholders wishing to find specific tools having to search nine separate toolboxes.

This tool inventory or "[virtual toolbox](#)" is available on the Network website and allows users to search through the tools, using an easy-to-use classification system. As projects add their tools, links to the location of each tool, as well as a

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brief explanation of its use are included. Regular updates about the toolbox are communicated through news pieces and the newsletters.

In closing, based on the approaches to define the policy strategy and the outlined updates, EHEN will continue to explore possibilities to make research results and evidence available so that they can support policy-making processes. This will guide not only a common strategy, but also project specific strategies at different scale levels, to use new evidence for better preventive policies toward improving citizens' health and well-being, while reducing inequalities.